

Concentrated Solar Power (CSP)

Concentrated solar power (CSP), also referred to as solar thermal electricity (STE), uses mirrors or reflective surfaces to concentrate sunlight onto a receiver, where the solar energy is collected and converted into heat. This thermal energy can be used to produce electricity or deliver heat directly for industrial processes. Unlike solar photovoltaic (PV) technology, CSP plants use turbines connected to generators to convert heat into electrical power and can store thermal energy for later conversion to electricity.

Project start:
October 2025

PROJECT COORDINATOR

CENER

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CONSORTIUM

MORE INFORMATION

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Smart Use of Novel Digital Tools for advanced performance and reduced costs in CSP tower plants

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About SUN-DT

SUN-DT is a Horizon Europe project aimed at increasing the competitiveness of the European CSP tower plants sector, as well as that of its supplier digitalisation companies.

SUN-DT Platform

SUN-DT will advance and integrate four interoperable innovative digital tools into a unified **SUN-DT Platform**:

- **HELIOSTATACC**: A heliostat automatic calibration and characterisation tool
- **SUN-DTWIN**: A Digital Twin of the solar field and receiver for automated decision-making
- **D-OPT**: An energy management system for dispatch optimisation system based on weather, and market and auxiliary services forecasts
- **PREDOM**: A predictive operation and maintenance (O&M) tool

Project duration:
3 years

Demonstrators

The **SUN-DT Platform** will be tested and validated at two experimental facilities and two commercial plants, representing different CSP tower configurations.

Cerro Dominador's CSP plant with O&M services provided by ACCIONA

Khi Solar One CSP plant owned by a consortium led by COX, with O&M services provided by COX

DLR's Solar Towers Jülich

IMDEA Energy's Very High Concentration Solar Tower

How SUN-DT empowers CSP

Lower Costs, Higher Efficiency
Smart digital controls boost energy yields while reducing operational downtime.

Smarter Operations
Predictive tools detect issues early and optimise plant performance through data-driven decisions.

Field-Proven Results
Validation in real commercial plants across different CSP tower configurations.

Strengthening European Industry
Enhances competitiveness of European CSP and digital industries through home-grown innovation.

Quantifiable objectives

- Increased power plant efficiency by 4-10%
- Enhanced yield performance of CSP tower plants by 5% (annually)
- Reduced operating and maintenance costs of the solar field (OPEX solar field) by 15%
- Reduced Capital of Expenditures (CAPEX) by 3%
- Increased profitability of the CSP tower plants by 5%